

ROLE OF XYLOPIR-T POLYPHENOL IN Ca^{2+} - TRIGGERED MITOCHONDRIAL MEGAPORE OPENING.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17452962>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23rd October 2025

Accepted: 24th October 2025

Online: 25th October 2025

KEYWORDS

Liver mitochondria, megapore, polyphenolic compounds.

ABSTRACT

Mitochondria are vital organelles responsible for cellular metabolism, and their functional state changes under the influence of calcium ions, reactive oxygen species, and various biologically active compounds. Excessive accumulation of Ca^{2+} ions in mitochondria triggers the opening of the Ca^{2+} -dependent mitochondrial megapore, leading to membrane potential depolarization and the release of apoptotic proteins. In this study, the effect of the polyphenol Xylopir-T on the process of Ca^{2+} -induced mitochondrial megapore opening was investigated. The results demonstrated that Xylopir-T polyphenol exhibits dose-dependent inhibitory, membrane-stabilizing, and protective properties against Ca^{2+} -induced mitochondrial permeability transition.

Introduction. Succinate-induced membrane potential-dependent reverse electron transport increases mitochondrial sensitivity to megapore opening. Succinate-induced depolarization of mitochondrial membrane potential inhibits reverse electron transport. Complex I-regulated respiration is weakened by mitochondrial megapore opening, but activity is maintained with the participation of complex II-bound substrates, consistent with inhibition of complex I-mediated respiration by NADH leakage from the mitochondrial matrix. Reactive oxygen species generated in complex III of the respiratory chain do not increase mitochondrial sensitivity to megapore opening. Thus, metabolic flux and the cellular metabolic environment mediate the functional mitochondrial response to excessive Ca^{2+} accumulation.

Materials and Methods. Mitochondria were isolated from the livers of healthy rats by the differential centrifugation method [1,2]. The incubation medium contained 5 mM succinate (substrate for complex II of the respiratory chain) and 2 μ M rotenone (inhibitor of complex I) [3]. The opening of the mitochondrial megapore was induced by Ca^{2+} ions at concentrations ranging from 10 to 50 μ M [4]. The Xylopir-T polyphenol was applied at concentrations of 50, 100, 150, and 200 μ M. The conformational state of the megapore and mitochondrial swelling were assessed spectrophotometrically at 540 nm, based on changes in optical density [5]. An incubation medium without polyphenol was used as the control. Statistical analysis was performed based on five independent experimental replicates, and the data were expressed as mean \pm standard error.

Results. The Xylopir-T polyphenol exerted a significant effect on the process of mitochondrial megapore opening. Experimental data demonstrated that Xylopir-T blocked the transition of the megapore to its open conformational state in a dose-dependent manner. The half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) of Xylopir-T was determined to be $167.6 \pm 5.2 \mu\text{M}$.

These findings indicate that Xylopir-T effectively inhibits Ca^{2+} -induced mitochondrial megapore opening and contributes to the stabilization and preservation of mitochondrial membrane integrity.

Conclusion. The obtained results indicate that Xylopir-T polyphenol acts as a dose-dependent inhibitor of the Ca^{2+} -induced opening of the mitochondrial megapore. It helps maintain mitochondrial membrane stability, limiting conformational changes that lead to mitochondrial depolarization and apoptosis. Therefore, Xylopir-T can be considered a potential anti-apoptotic and cytoprotective compound, capable of protecting mitochondria from oxidative stress and Ca^{2+} overload.

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